

Synthesis and fungicidal activity of 4,4'-bis[(2''-arylthiazolo[4,3-*b*]-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5''-yl)methoxy]bibenzyls

I. R. Siddiqui, Smriti Dwivedi*, Pawan K. Shukla and Pravin K. Singh

Laboratory of Green Technology, Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad,

Allahabad-211 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : smriti96@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 14 July 2004, revised 18 July 2004, accepted 9 September 2005

Abstract : Several 4,4'-bis(2''-aryl-4''-thiazolidinon-3''-yl-*N*-acetamidoxy)bibenzyls (4a-h) and 4,4'-bis[2''-arylthiazolo[4,3-*b*]-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5''-yl)methoxy]bibenzyls (5a-h) have been synthesized and tested for their antifungal activity.

Keywords : Bibenzyls, synthesis, fungicidal activity.

1,3,4-Oxadiazoles and thiazoles^{1(a,b)} are known to possess various biological activities. Prompted by these observations, we undertook the synthesis of heterocyclic compound in which both oxadiazole and thiazole moieties are present, when these moieties are attached with bibenzyl, which itself is antifungal, its activity increases many folds.

Results and discussion

Refluxion of 4,4'-ethylenebisphenol in dry acetone with chloroacetic acid and potassium carbonate gave 4,4'-ethylenebisphenoxyacetic acid **1** which on refluxing with hydrazine hydrate yielded 4,4'-bis(methoxycarbohydrazide)bibenzyl **2**. The last compound on condensation with different aromatic aldehydes gave 4,4'-bis(arylidinylaminoacetamidoxy)bibenzyls **3a-h**. Compounds **3a-h** through intramolecular cyclocondensation with mercaptoacetic acid gave 4,4'-bis(2''-aryl-4''-thiazolidinon-3''-yl-*N*-acetamidoxy)bibenzyls **4a-h** which on oxidative cyclisation with conc. H₂SO₄ and ammonia solution gave 4,4'-bis[(2''-arylthiazolo[4,3-*b*]-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5''-yl)methoxy]bibenzyls **5a-h**.

Compounds **4a-h** and **5a-h** were screened for their antifungal activity against *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Aspergillus niger* at 10, 100 and 1000 ppm concentration by Agar plate technique^{1b}. A commercial fungicide Dithane M-45 was also tested under similar conditions for comparing the results. Among the tested compounds, **4e**, **4f**, **5b** and **5e** were found to be most active against both the test fungus (Table 1).

Experimental

M.ps. were taken in open capillaries and are uncor-

rected. ¹H NMR were recorded by using DMSO-*d*₆ on a Bruker DRX-300 (300 MHz FTNMR) spectrometer using TMS as internal reference. Yields, melting point and spectral data are recorded in Table 2.

4,4'-Ethylenebisphenoxyacetic acid (**1**) :

Following the standard procedure² to a solution of 0.03 mol of ethylene bisphenol³ in dry acetone (25 ml), anhydrous K₂CO₃ (10 g) and chloroacetic acid (0.03 mol) was added and refluxed on a water-bath with stirring for 12-13 h under reduced pressure. The product was filtered, dried and crystallised from ethanol, (65%), m.p. 260 °C; ν_{\max} 1680 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 1030 cm⁻¹ (-C-O-C-); δ (DMSO) 4.91 (4H, OCH₂), 7.4 (8H, ArH), 2.81 (4H, CH₂CH₂), 10.5 (2H, COOH).

4,4'-Bis(methoxycarbohydrazide)bibenzyl (**2**) :

Following the standard procedure² a mixture of **1** (0.05 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.06 mol) in absolute ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath. After refluxing for 4 h excess of ethanol distilled off, the solid mass thus obtained are filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol, (59%), m.p. 100 °C; ν_{\max} 3300-3100 (NH-NH₂), 1650 (CONH), 1055-1256 cm⁻¹ (-C-O-C-); δ (DMSO) 7.9 (8H, ArH), 2.81 (4H, CH₂CH₂), 4.94 (4H, OCH₂), 8.1 (2H, NHCO), 4.65-5.25 (4H, NH₂).

4,4'-Bis(arylidinylaminoacetamidoxy)bibenzyl (**3a-h**) :

Following the standard procedure⁴ a mixture of **2** (0.01 mol), verataldehyde (0.01 mol) and a few drops of glacial acetic acid in ethanol (10 ml) was refluxed for 5 h and then cooled. The resulting solid was washed with cold ethanol and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol to

Table 1. Antifungal screening results of compounds 4a-h and 5a-h

Compd.	Average % inhibition after 96 h against					
	<i>A. niger</i>			<i>F. oxysporum</i>		
	1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm	1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm
4a	62	30	15	58	32	18
4b	52	34	12	50	31	10
4c	70	54	27	68	51	25
4d	60	49	17	64	43	42
4e	82	65	43	86	69	42
4f	100	82	52	100	78	51
4g	72	56	31	71	55	30
4h	61	38	19	59	34	12
5a	73	49	32	71	47	33
5b	100	67	51	100	70	53
5c	66	43	21	62	40	12
5d	61	41	24	68	45	18
5e	89	53	42	87	55	39
5f	71	44	35	75	50	37
5g	73	46	39	70	49	26
5h	65	38	22	67	34	29

Table 2. Physical and spectral data of compounds 3, 4, 5(b-h)

Compd.	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	IR (ν_{\max} cm ⁻¹)	¹ H NMR (δ)
3b	65	165	3300 (N-H), 1680 (C=O), 1285 (C-O-C)	2.87 (4H, CH ₂ CH ₂), 3.93 (6H, OCH ₃), 7.12–7.65 (16H, ArH), 8.25 (2H, CH=N), 4.95 (4H, CH ₂ CH ₂), 8.1 (2H, NH-CO)
3c	58	205	3300 (N-H), 1680 (C=O), 1285 (C-O-C)	2.85 (4H, CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.21–7.53 (16H, ArH), 8.29 (2H, CH=N), 12.1 (2H, ArOH), 4.95 (4H, OCH ₂), 8.1 (2H, NH-CO)
3d	53	195	3300 (N-H), 1680 (C=O), 1285 (C-O-C)	2.85 (4H, CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.21–7.53 (16H, ArH), 8.31 (2H, CH=N), 16.69 (2H, ArOH), 4.95 (4H, OCH ₂), 8.03 (2H, NH-CO)
3e	56	185	3300 (N-H), 1680 (C=O), 1285 (C-O-C)	2.87 (4H, CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.12–7.83 (16H, ArH), 8.31 (2H, CH=N), 4.95 (4H, OCH ₂), 8.12 (2H, NH-CO)
3f	62	180	3300 (N-H), 1680 (C=O), 1285 (C-O-C)	2.82 (4H, CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.08–7.25 (16H, ArH), 8.33 (2H, CH=N), 4.96 (4H, OCH ₂), 8.12 (2H, NH-CO)
3g	50	165	3300 (N-H), 1680 (C=O), 1285 (C-O-C)	2.82 (4H, CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.10–7.25 (14H, ArH), 8.33 (2H, CH=N), 4.96 (4H, OCH ₂), 4.96 (6H, OCH ₃), 11.67 (2H, ArOH), 3.93 (6H, OCH ₃), 8.12 (2H, NH-CO)
3h	58	210	3300 (N-H), 1680 (C=O), 1285 (C-O-C)	2.82 (4H, CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.10–7.25 (18H, ArH), 8.33 (2H, CH=N), 4.96 (4H, OCH ₂), 4.96 (6H, OCH ₃), 8.12 (2H, NH-CO)

Note

Table-2 (contd)

4b	48	160	3300 (N-H), 1700 (C=O thiazolidinone moiety), 1670 (C=O), 1275 (C-O-C), 605 (C-S-C)	2 87 (4H, CH ₂ CH ₂), 3 93 (6H, OCH ₃), 7 12-7 65 (16H, ArH), 4 90 (4H, OCH ₂), 5 50 (2H, cyclic S-CH-N) 4 30 (4H, cyclic CO-CH ₂ -S), 8 23 (2H NH-CO)
4c	53	200	3300 (N-H), 1700 (C=O thiazolidinone moiety), 1670 (C=O), 1275 (C-O-C), 605 (C-S-C)	2 85 (4H, CH ₂ CH ₂), 7 21-7 53 (16H, ArH) 12 12 (2H, ArOH), 5 95 (2H, cyclic S-CH-N), 4 90 (4H, OCH ₂), 8 23 (2H, NH-CO), 4 30 (4H, cyclic CO-CH ₂ -S)
4d	55	182	3300 (N-H), 1700 (C=O thiazolidinone moiety), 1670 (C=O), 1275 (C-O-C), 605 (C-S-C)	2 85 (4H, CH ₂ CH ₂), 7 21-7 53 (16H ArH), 11 69 (2H, ArOH), 4 95 (2H, OCH ₂), 8 03 (2H, NH-CO), 4 30 (4H, cyclic CO-CH ₂ -S), 5 95 (2H, cyclic S-CH-N)
4e	60	180	3300 (N-H), 1700 (C=O thiazolidinone moiety), 1670 (C=O), 1275 (C-O-C), 605 (C-S-C)	2 87 (4H, CH ₂ CH ₂), 7 25-7 97 (16H, ArH) 4 97 (4H, OCH ₂), 8 01 (2H, NH-CO), 4 30 (4H, CO-CH ₂ -S), 5 95 (2H, cyclic S-CH-N)
4f	59	217	3300 (N-H) 1700 (C=O thiazolidinone moiety), 1670 (C=O), 1275 (C-O-C), 605 (C-S-C)	2 89 (4H, CH ₂ CH ₂), 7 25-7 96 (16H, ArH), 4 95 (4H, OCH ₂), 8 01 (2H, NH-CO), 4 30 (4H, CO-CH ₂ -S), 5 92 (2H, cyclic S-CH-N)
4g	65	190	3300 (N-H), 1700 (C=O thiazolidinone moiety), 1670 (C=O), 1275 (C-O-C), 605 (C-S-C)	2 87 (4H, acyclic CH ₂ CH ₂), 7 25-7 96 (14H, ArH), 4 95 (4H, OCH ₂), 8 01 (2H, NH-CO), 4 30 (4H, COCH ₂ -S), 5 92 (2H, cyclic S-CH-N), 11 69 (2H, ArOH), 3 93 (6H, OCH ₃)
4h	60	125	3300 (N-H), 1700 (C=O thiazolidinone moiety), 1670 (C=O), 1275 (C-O-C), 605 (C-S-C)	2 87 (4H, acyclic CH ₂ CH ₂), 7 25-7 96 (18H, ArH), 4 95 (4H, OCH ₂), 8 01 (2H, NH-CO), 4 30 (4H, CO-CH ₂ -S), 5 92 (2H, cyclic S-CH-N)

Table-2 (contd.)

5b	63	175	1275 (-C-O-C-)	2.86 (4H, acyclic CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.12-7.63 (16H, ArH), 3.93 (6H, OCH ₃), 4.92 (4H, OCH ₂), 5.6 (2H, cyclic S-CH-N), 4.7-5.3 (2H, C=CH)
5c	58	190	1275 (-C-O-C-)	2.86 (4H, acyclic CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.12-7.63 (16H, ArH), 12.13 (2H, ArOH), 4.92 (4H, OCH ₂), 5.62 (2H, cyclic S-CH-N), 4.7-5.3 (2H, C=CH)
5d	57	135	1275 (-C-O-C-)	2.86 (4H, acyclic CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.12-7.83 (16H, ArH), 4.91 (4H, OCH ₂), 5.62 (2H, cyclic S-CH-N), 4.7-5.3 (2H, C=CH)
5e	65	115	1275 (-C-O-C-)	2.86 (4H, acyclic CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.12-7.83 (16H, ArH), 4.91 (4H, OCH ₂), 5.62 (2H, cyclic S-CH-N), 4.7-5.3 (2H, C=CH)
5f	55	173	1275 (-C-O-C-)	2.85 (4H, acyclic CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.25-7.56 (16H, ArH), 4.91 (4H, OCH ₂), 5.60 (2H, S-CH-N), 4.7-5.2 (2H, C=CH)
5g	50	165	1275 (-C-O-C-)	2.85 (4H, acyclic CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.25-7.63 (14H, ArH), 12.13 (2H, ArOH), 4.92 (4H, OCH ₂), 5.62 (2H, S-CH-N), 4.7-5.3 (2H, C=CH), 3.91 (6H, OCH ₃)
5h	56	145	1275 (-C-O-C-)	2.85 (4H, acyclic CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.25-7.50 (18H, ArH), 4.91 (4H, OCH ₂), 5.60 (2H, cyclic S-CH-N), 4.7-5.2 (2H, C=CH)

Compd.	R'
3,4,5a	3,4-(CH ₃ O) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃
b	4-CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄
c	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄
d	4-OH.C ₆ H ₄
e	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄
f	4-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄
g	4-OH-3-CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₃
h	C ₆ H ₅

Reagents : (i) ClCH₂COOH.K₂CO₃/dry acetone, (ii) NH₂NH₂, (iii) R'-CH=O, (iv) HS-CH₂COOH, (v) conc. H₂SO₄/liq NH₃, 0-5 °C

Scheme 1

Note

get **3a**. (61%), m.p. 65 °C. Anal. Found : C, 66.04; H, 6.39; N, 8.55 (C₃₆H₃₈O₈N₄); ν_{\max} 3300 (NH), 1680 (C=O), 1030, 1245 (C-O-C); δ (DMSO) 2.89 (4H, CH₂CH₂), 3.93 (6H, OCH₃), 7.12–7.85 (14H, ArH), 8.28 (2H, CH=N), 4.95 (4H, OCH₂), 8.1 (2H, NH-CO), M⁺ 598. Other compounds **3b-h** were synthesized by a similar procedure using various aromatic aldehydes.

4,4'-Bis(2''-aryl-4''-thiazolidinon-3''-yl-N-acetamidoxy)bibenzyl (4a-h) :

Following the standard procedure⁴ a mixture of **3a** (0.01 mol) and thioglycollic acid (0.01 mol) in dioxane (30 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. The excess dioxane was then distilled off under reduced pressure and the residue poured into ice-cold water. The solid, thus, obtained was washed with 10% NaHCO₃ solution, finally with water and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol to give **4a**, (57%), m.p. 165 °C. Anal. Found : C, 59.83; H, 5.27; N, 6.97 (C₄₀H₄₂N₄O₁₀S₂); ν_{\max} 3300 (N-H), 1700 (C=O thiazolidinone moiety), 1670 (C=O), 1275 (-C-O-C-), 605 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C); δ (DMSO) 2.89 (4H, CH₂CH₂), 3.95 (6H, OCH₃), 7.12–7.85 (14H, ArH), 5.92 (2H, S-CH-N), 4.95 (4H, OCH₂), 4.30 (4H, COCH₂-S), M⁺ 802. The compounds **4b-h** were synthesized from **3b-h** by a similar procedure.

4,4'-Bis[(2''-arylthiazolo[4,3-b]-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5''-yl)methoxy]bibenzyl (5a-h) :

Compound **4a** were treated with minimum amount of cold H₂SO₄, so that gummy mass was formed. It was kept at room temp. for 1 h, the solution then poured over

crushed ice. The resulting enols were filtered, washed with water and dried. After that ammonia solution was added till it became slightly basic. It was then filtered, washed with cold water and crystallised from alcohol to gave **5a**, (50%), m.p. 270 °C. Anal. Found C, 62.81; H, 4.74; N, 7.32 (C₄₀H₃₆O₈N₄S₂); ν_{\max} 1275 (-C-O-C), δ (DMSO) 2.86 (4H, CH₂CH₂), 3.93 (6H, OCH₃), 7.12–7.65 (14H, ArH), 4.92 (4H, OCH₂), 5.6 (2H, S-CH-N), M⁺ 764. Similarly compounds **5b-h** were synthesized from **4b-h** by a similar procedure.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad for providing laboratory facilities and RSIC, CDRI, Lucknow for providing spectral data.

References

- 1 (a) V V Laddi, S R Desai, R S Bennur and S C Bennur, *Indian J Hetero Chem*, 2002, **11**, 319, R N Vansoddia, H J Virani and H Parekh, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 1985, **65**, 782, C L Patel and H Parekh, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 1981, **65**, 606, (b) V N Patelia, P K Patel and A J Baxi, *J Indian Chem Soc.*, 1990, **67**, 780, T Koho, *Chem Abstr*, 1971, **75**, 117867; G J Horsetfall, *Bot Rev*, 1945, **11**, 357
- 2 H Oza, D Joshi and H Parekh, *Indian J Chem, Sect B*, 1998, **37**, 822
- 3 R C Fuson and H O House, *J. Am Chem Soc*, 1953, **75**, 1325
- 4 I R Siddiqui, P K Singh, J Singh and J Singh, *J Agric Food Chem.*, 2003, **51**, 7062